

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

CTHRC1

(Collagen Triple Helix Repeat Containing 1)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	115908/ Q96CG8
Target Nominator	TREAT-AD, AMP-AD
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Therapeutic Area(s)	Alzheimer's disease
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CONTENTS OF TEP

Bioinformatic analysis: Target source & hypothesis

Protein constructs & expression methods: Full-length protein produced in Expi293F cells.

TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target is found within a TMT proteomics network module that was highly correlated with cognition. This module (Module 42) contains several novel AD targets, including SMOC1 and SFRP1.

TREAT-AD Target Risk Score: 2.98 (rank #5140, 79.4th percentile)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target's general relevance to Alzheimer's Disease, and is the sum of the target's Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for this target is 2.98 out of 5 (rank #5140, 79.4th percentile). The individual score components include 1.02 of 3 for genetics, and 1.97 out of 2 for genomics. The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of CTHRC1 RNA is significantly decreased, while CTHRC1 protein is significantly increased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. CTHRC1 is annotated to GO terms from the Structural Satbilization domain.

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Seattle Alzheimer's Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD). The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins. The expression of the target in subtypes within each broad class is shown as a point. Blue points show the summary expression of cells from individuals with no dementia, while red points show summary metrics of cells from dementia patients. Open circles reflect low confidence measures of expression.

The expression of CTHRC1 is not confidently detected in any cell types within this dataset.

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

CTHRC1 is a novel member of the collagen family that was identified with other collagen isoforms within the deep brain proteomics studies on postmortem brains in which it mapped onto a core proteomic module linked with cognitive decline and AD neuropathological progression (1). The interactions between CTHRC1 and AD are discussed below and are suggestive of a complex role in AD progression, but much work will need to be done to verify that possibility. In this project we have developed a set of resources

known as a target enablement package (TEP) that include validation of CTHRC1 binding antibodies with high specificity that are appropriate for both immunohistology and biochemistry, purified protein, and a full bioinformatics work up of the gene, its AD risk, cell expression pattern, and biological process affiliations (see above). The goal of TREAT-AD is to provide these TEPs to the scientific community to foster investigations into promising targets with a diminished barrier to operationalizing these future studies.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

CTHRC1 (Collagen Triple Helix Repeat Containing 1) is a protein involved in various physiological and pathological processes. CTHRC1 is a secreted glycoprotein comprising approximately 243 amino acids, with an N-terminal signal peptide directing the protein to the secretory pathway (2, 3). CTHRC1 undergoes complex patterns of glycosylation, which is likely essential for its stability and biological function (4). The protein has a collagen triple helix repeat domain, characteristic of collagen-like proteins, which may facilitate its interaction with other extracellular matrix components (2, 3, 5, 6). The C-terminal region of the protein might be involved in its functional interactions with cell surface receptors or other proteins.

CTHRC1 has multiple different biological roles including regulation of extracellular matrix during tissue repair and development, at least partially through the ECM mediated direction of cell migration patterns and resultant tissue architecture (4). CTHRC1 interacts with the Wnt/ β -catenin signaling pathway during development to promote proliferation and differentiation of numerous cell lineages within the CNS (7-9). The modulation of ECM and Wnt-signaling may coordinately contribute to the CNS developmental programs, potentially facilitating proper neuronal migration and synaptic connective requisite for brain function. The modulation of ECM structure and Wnt-signaling may also be involved in synaptic connectivity and strengthening in the adult brain, as well, suggesting a plausible functional role in synaptic support across age. The role of CTHRC1 in driving schwann cell proliferation and coordinate inhibition of nerve myelination further highlights the potential significance of its role in neurodevelopment and synaptic maintenance (10, 11). Further, long-term use of anti-inflammatory TNF blockade drugs in developing mice demonstrate a decrease in microglial progenitor proliferation, decreases in microglia, and increased numbers of both neurons and neuroproliferative zones in tight association with decrements in CTHRC1 and FRZB (12), further suggesting complex role of CTHRC1 in neurodevelopmental processes. CTHRC1 regulation of Wnt-signaling demonstrates a convergence point with AD, as Wnt-signaling is implicated in AD pathological progression (13, 14).

CTHRC1 may play a role in vascular remodeling and repair (2, 15-17), in both development and adult organisms, suggesting another convergence point with AD, as cardiovascular disease is a known AD risk factor (18, 19), and white matter hyperintensities associated with microvascular infarcts are common in AD (20, 21). Wnt pathways and ECM structure both play a role in the regulation of APP proteolytic processing, implying a potential role for CTHRC1 in the regulation of APP signaling and amyloid production (22-24). Given that Wnt-signal is also inked with Tau phosphorylation and aggregation (25, 26), CTHRC1 is plausibly connected to synaptic viability, amyloid production and tau-phosphorylation, supporting a possible role for CTHRC1 in AD pathogenesis. Consequently, CTHRC1 was identified within our work as a member of a 32-protein proteomic module strongly associated with both cognitive decline and AD pathological progression (1).

RESULTS – THE TEP

Proteins Purified

1. CTHRC1-c001: Full-length Human CTHRC1 (E31-E243) without signalling sequence. Contains a C-terminal 6His and AviTag (allowing in vitro biotinylation, if needed). Protein produced in Expi293F cells.

2. CTHRC1-c002: [Human CTHRC1 \(E101-E243\)](#). Contains a C-terminal 6His and AviTag (allowing in vitro biotinylation, if needed). Protein produced in Expi293F cells.

See **Additional information (section 1)** with details of plasmid expression constructs and purification procedures.

CONCLUSION

The tools presented here provide a foundation for further biological investigation of the role of CTHRC1 in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

The work performed by the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center has been funded by the National Institute on Aging through grant U54 AG065187.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Materials and Methods

Protein expression constructs and protein purification

All relevant plasmids are available on addgene: [TREAT-AD plasmid collection](#)

1. **CTHRC1-c001:** Full-length Human CTHRC1 (E31-E243) without signalling sequence. Contains a C-terminal 6His and AviTag (allowing in vitro biotinylation, if needed). Protein produced in Expi293F cells.

Construct ID	CTHRC1-c001
Parental vector	pHL-avitag3
Tag	C-terminal His6, C-terminal Avitag
Protein mass (with tag and secretion signal)	29765.8 Da
Extinction Coefficient (M⁻¹ cm⁻¹)	41940
Protein sequence (with tag)	MGILPSPGMPALLSLVSLLSVLLMGCVAETGSEIPKGGKQKAQLRQREVVDLYNGMC LQGPAGVPGRDGGSPGANGIPGTPGIPGRDGFKEKGECLRESFEESWTPNYKQCS WSSLNYGIDLGKIAECTFTKMRSNSALRVLFSGSLRLKCRNACCQRWYFTFNGAEC SGPLPIEAIYLDQGSPENSTINIHRSSVEGLCEGIGAGLVDVAIWVGTCSDYPKG DASTGWNSVSRIIIIEELPKGTGGSGGSLNDIFEAQKIEWHEGRTKHHHHHH

2. CTHRC1-c002: Human CTHRC1 (E101-E243). Contains a C-terminal 6His and AviTag (allowing in vitro biotinylation, if needed). Protein produced in Expi293F cells.

Construct ID	CTHRC1-c002
Parental vector	pHL-avitag3
Tag	C-terminal His6, C-terminal Avitag
Protein mass (with tag and secretion signal)	22415.6 Da
Extinction Coefficient (M⁻¹ cm⁻¹)	40450
Protein sequence (with tag)	MGILPSPGMPALLSLVSLLSVLLMGCVAETGSWTPNYKQCSWSSLNYGIDLGKIAE CTFTKMRSNSALRVLFSGSLRLKCRNACCQRWYFTFNGAECGPLPIEAIYLDQGS PEMNSTINIHRSSVEGLCEGIGAGLVDVAIWVGTCSDYPKGDASTGWNSVSRIII ELPKGTGGSGGSLNDIFEAQKIEWHEGRTKHHHHHH

CTHRC1-c002:

**Intact Mass
Deconvolution:
GPNMB-c200 (with
tag)**

N/A

Observed Mass:

Protein yield:	1.3mg/L of culture (for CTHRC1-c001), 2.1 mg/L of culture (for CTHRC1-c002)
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Expression and Purification Protocol	
Expression host	<i>Mammalian</i> : Expi293F cells (Thermo Fisher Scientific)
Expression medium	FreeStyle 293 Expression Medium (Thermo Fisher Scientific)
Plasmid purification	Transform the construct into the <i>E. coli</i> strain MACH1. Plate on LB-agar plates containing ampicillin (100 µg/ml). Inoculate 5 ml LB broth containing ampicillin (100 ug/ml) with a single colony and grow 6h at 37°C with shaking. Inoculate 800 ml LB broth containing the same antibiotic with 2 ml of starter culture and grow overnight at 37°C with shaking. Split culture into 4 and perform MaxiPrep (Qiagen) with 4 columns according to manufacturer's instructions. Add 0.7 volumes of isopropanol to precipitate the plasmid. Spin (17000g, 30 min, 4°C) and wash pellet with 70% ethanol. Resuspend plasmid with sterile TE buffer under sterile conditions. Yield is typically 2 mg of plasmid.
Transfection	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Split Expi293F cells to 1x10⁶ cells/ml in 200 ml FreeStyle 293 Expression Medium. Incubate for 24 h until cells are approximately 2x10⁶ cells/ml (37°C, 150 rpm, 8% CO₂, 75% rh). 2. Add plasmid to 4mL of pre-warmed Opti-MEM at 0.5 µg/ml final concentration. 3. Add linear PEI (1 mg/ml sterile stock) to another 4mL of pre-warmed Opti-MEM at 3 µg/ml final concentration. 4. Add the mixture from Step 3 to the one in Step 2 and incubate at room temperature for 30 min. 5. Add the plasmid/PEI mixture slowly to the cells. 6. Add sodium butyrate (1 M sterile stock) to 12 mM final concentration. 7. Incubate cells at 30°C (8%CO₂/75% rh) with shaking at 150 rpm. 8. Harvest cell culture supernatant at 5 days post transfection (900g, 20 min, 4°C). 9. Filter supernatant through 0.2 µm filter.
Purification buffers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ni IMAC W10 buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 10 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol 2. Ni IMAC W25 buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 25 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol 3. Ni IMAC elution buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 250 mM imidazole, 2% glycerol 4. Size exclusion chromatography elution buffer : dPBS (from ThermoFisher) 5. Ni-sepharose beads, equilibrated in Ni IMAC W10 buffer.
Purification step 1: IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Add imidazole to filtered supernatant to 10 mM final concentration.

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Add a total of 2.5 ml equilibrated Ni-sepharose beads to the cell supernatant, split into 50-ml falcon tubes. Mix by rotation for 1 hr in a cold room. 3. Spin beads/supernatant slurry (700g, 5 min, 4°C). Decant supernatant and wash beads with 100 ml W10 buffer. Repeat wash with 50 ml W10. Spin again and transfer beads to gravity column in a cold room. 4. Wash column with 25 ml W25. 5. Elute protein with 1x 10 ml elution buffer, followed by 2x5 ml elution buffer. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay. Pool elution fractions containing protein.
Purification step 2: Size Exclusion Chromatography	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Concentrate pooled IMAC elution fractions to 1 ml using a centrifugal concentrator with the appropriate MWCO. 2. Perform SEC on a HiLoad Superdex S200 HR 16/60 column, equilibrated in DPBS, at 1 ml/min. 3. Analyse fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity and concentrate to 1-5 mg/ml, as measured by UV spectroscopy. 4. Snap-freeze aliquots in thin-walled PCR tubes in liquid N₂, and store at -80°C.

References

1. Toomey BH, Mitrovic SA, Lindner-Liaw M, Leon Vazquez RG, Kacer D, Ryzhov S, et al. Activated CTHRC1 promotes glycolysis in endothelial cells: Implications for metabolism and angiogenesis. *Vascul Pharmacol.* 2023;153:107246.
2. Bella J, Hulmes DJ. Fibrillar Collagens. *Subcell Biochem.* 2017;82:457-90.
3. Leclère L, Nir TS, Bazarsky M, Braitbard M, Schneidman-Duhovny D, Gat U. Dynamic Evolution of the Cthrc1 Genes, a Newly Defined Collagen-Like Family. *Genome Biol Evol.* 2020;12(2):3957-70.
4. Squire JM, Parry DA. Fibrous Protein Structures: Hierarchy, History and Heroes. *Subcell Biochem.* 2017;82:1-33.
5. Karsdal MA, Nielsen SH, Leeming DJ, Langholm LL, Nielsen MJ, Manon-Jensen T, et al. The good and the bad collagens of fibrosis - Their role in signaling and organ function. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev.* 2017;121:43-56.
6. Li Y, Xing BX, Wang YH, Yu S, Zhao H, Lv QQ, Lu CX. CTHRC1 promotes growth, migration and invasion of trophoblasts via reciprocal Wnt/beta-catenin regulation. *J Cell Commun Signal.* 2022;16(1):63-74.
7. Yamamoto S, Nishimura O, Misaki K, Nishita M, Minami Y, Yonemura S, et al. Cthrc1 selectively activates the planar cell polarity pathway of Wnt signaling by stabilizing the Wnt-receptor complex. *Dev Cell.* 2008;15(1):23-36.
8. Kelley MW. Leading Wnt down a PCP path: Cthrc1 acts as a coreceptor in the Wnt-PCP pathway. *Dev Cell.* 2008;15(1):7-8.
9. Chen P, Cescon M, Bonaldo P. The Role of Collagens in Peripheral Nerve Myelination and Function. *Mol Neurobiol.* 2015;52(1):216-25.
10. Apra C, Richard L, Couplier F, Blugeon C, Gilardi-Hebenstreit P, Vallat JM, et al. Cthrc1 is a negative regulator of myelination in Schwann cells. *Glia.* 2012;60(3):393-403.
11. Yli-Karjanmaa M, Larsen KS, Fenger CD, Kristensen LK, Martin NA, Jensen PT, et al. TNF deficiency causes alterations in the spatial organization of neurogenic zones and alters the number of microglia and neurons in the cerebral cortex. *Brain Behav Immun.* 2019;82:279-97.

12. Dutta A, Bhattacharya P, Chutia P, Borah A. Targeting of wnt signalling pathway by small bioactive molecules for the treatment of Alzheimer's disease. *In Silico Pharmacol.* 2024;12(1):50.
13. Dong L, Hou B, Liu C, Mao C, Huang X, Shang L, et al. Association Between Wnt Target Genes and Cortical Volumes in Alzheimer's Disease. *J Mol Neurosci.* 2023;73(11-12):1010-6.
14. Yuan X, Duan X, Li Z, Yao B, Enhejirigala, Song W, et al. Collagen triple helix repeat containing-1 promotes functional recovery of sweat glands by inducing adjacent microvascular network reconstruction in vivo. *Burns Trauma.* 2022;10:tkac035.
15. Liu K, Li X, Yang Z, Zhang R. Activation of CTHRC1 by HOXB9 Promotes Angiogenesis through Fatty Acid Metabolism in Lung Adenocarcinoma. *Rev Invest Clin.* 2022;75(2):63-75.
16. Buga AM, Margaritescu C, Scholz CJ, Radu E, Zelenak C, Popa-Wagner A. Transcriptomics of post-stroke angiogenesis in the aged brain. *Front Aging Neurosci.* 2014;6:44.
17. Dougherty RJ, Jonaitis EM, Gaitan JM, Lose SR, Mergen BM, Johnson SC, et al. Cardiorespiratory fitness mitigates brain atrophy and cognitive decline in adults at risk for Alzheimer's disease. *Alzheimers Dement (Amst).* 2021;13(1):e12212.
18. Clark LR, Norton D, Berman SE, Johnson SC, Bendlin BB, Wieben O, et al. Association of Cardiovascular and Alzheimer's Disease Risk Factors with Intracranial Arterial Blood Flow in Whites and African Americans. *J Alzheimers Dis.* 2019;72(3):919-29.
19. Kumar VV, Huang H, Zhao L, Verble DD, Nutaitis A, Tharwani SD, et al. Baseline Results: The Association Between Cardiovascular Risk and Preclinical Alzheimer's Disease Pathology (ASCEND) Study. *J Alzheimers Dis.* 2020;75(1):109-17.
20. de Oliveira FF, Berretta JM, de Almeida Junior GV, de Almeida SS, Chen ES, Smith MC, Bertolucci PHF. Pharmacogenetic analyses of variations of measures of cardiovascular risk in Alzheimer's dementia. *Indian J Med Res.* 2019;150(3):261-71.
21. Zeng Q, Long Z, Feng M, Zhao Y, Luo S, Wang K, et al. Valproic Acid Stimulates Hippocampal Neurogenesis via Activating the Wnt/beta-Catenin Signaling Pathway in the APP/PS1/Nestin-GFP Triple Transgenic Mouse Model of Alzheimer's Disease. *Front Aging Neurosci.* 2019;11:62.
22. Elliott C, Rojo AI, Ribe E, Broadstock M, Xia W, Morin P, et al. A role for APP in Wnt signalling links synapse loss with beta-amyloid production. *Transl Psychiatry.* 2018;8(1):179.
23. Zhou F, Gong K, van Laar T, Gong Y, Zhang L. Wnt/beta-catenin signal pathway stabilizes APP intracellular domain (AICD) and promotes its transcriptional activity. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun.* 2011;412(1):68-73.
24. Wang J, Jing Y, Song L, Xing Y. Neuroprotective effects of Wnt/beta-catenin signaling pathway against Abeta -induced tau protein over-phosphorylation in PC12 cells. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun.* 2016;471(4):628-32.
25. Scali C, Caraci F, Gianfriddo M, Diodato E, Roncarati R, Pollio G, et al. Inhibition of Wnt signaling, modulation of Tau phosphorylation and induction of neuronal cell death by DKK1. *Neurobiol Dis.* 2006;24(2):254-65.
26. Johnson ECB, Carter EK, Dammer EB, Duong DM, Gerasimov ES, Liu Y, et al. Large-scale deep multi-layer analysis of Alzheimer's disease brain reveals strong proteomic disease-related changes not observed at the RNA level. *Nat Neurosci.* 2022;25(2):213-25.

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